

Adsorption of Toxic Metal Pollutants from Aquatic Environment by Banana Plant: A Review

Meena Chakraborty^{a,*}

Govt. Naveen College Bori, Durg, Chhattisgarh, India

*Corresponding Author: Govt. Naveen College Bori, Durg, Chhattisgarh, India
 E-mail Address: chakrabortymeena@gmail.com (Meena Chakraborty)

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Rapid industrialization and urbanization causes huge environmental damage. Pollution of aquatic environment is one of them. Heavy metals are one of the most noticeable contaminants in water, and they typically enter the environment via the discharge of industrial effluent. Since these metals are soluble in water, they can be easily absorbed by living organisms. Even minute quantities of heavy metals in the body can have devastating effects. For this reason, it is crucial to purify water by removing metals. This article defines the adsorption capacity, mechanism, factors affecting the adsorption process, and isothermal, kinetic, and thermodynamic characteristics of activated carbon and biochar generated from banana leaves, stalks, and stems for heavy metals (copper, lead, and cadmium).

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

Banana Plant in Toxic Metal Adsorption

Introduction

Financial growth and technological development in all over the world bring modernization along with enormous environmental issues [1]. One of the major issues is water pollution. Clean water is the necessity for humanity but because of urbanization and industrialization, availability of clean water has become a challenge for us. One of prominent water pollutant is heavy metal. Presence of small amount of heavy metal causes severe toxicity because of their solubility in water. Heavy metals trash was mostly generated from four sources: used batteries, metal ore processing, mining, and metal smelting. Heavy metals such as lead, cadmium, and copper are examples of pollutants that are released by industry into water bodies and subsequently contaminate these systems. The World Health Organization sets the safe level of lead (II) in water at 0.05 mg/L, cadmium (II) at 0.003 mg/L, and copper (II) at 1.5 mg/L. [2]. In other words, they become a danger to us if their concentration in water rises above the threshold we just discussed. Thus, it is crucial for people's health that these heavy metals be taken out of the water supply.

Heavy metals can be removed from water using a variety of techniques, some of which are expensive and/or complicated to operate, including as activated charcoal, reverse osmosis, oxidation, and nano filtration [3]. Being a cheap and non-hazardous technique, adsorption is among the top choices for purifying water from metal contaminants [4]. Many different types of adsorbents have been tried and tested for metal treatment, including activated carbon, amorphous silica, clay minerals, diatomite, charcoal, zeolites, polymers, carbon nanotubes, graphene oxide, reduced graphene oxide, and many others [5,6,7,8] The advantages of bioadsorbents over other adsorbents lie in their low cost, high adsorption efficiency, and low environmental impact.

Bananas are widely available, and they are the fourth most-cultivated food crop in the world, behind rice, wheat, and corn [9]. Following fruit harvest, the remaining banana plant stems and leaves are often left in the field to decompose over the course of a few months [10]. Banana stem and leaf (BSL) could be a promising raw material for biochar production due to their high lignin and low cellulose concentrations. Banana stalk, which is very fibrous, has been used to make activated carbon. Banana stem and leaf biochar

and activated carbon have a high fixed carbon content and porous structure [11,12]. As a result, they can function as an adsorbent for cleaning water of toxic metals. This paper will discuss the use of biochar and activated carbon made from banana stem, leaves, and stalk for the removal of hazardous metals such as Cu (II), Pb (II), and Cd (II) from water.

Health risk due to toxic pollutants

The rapid growth of industry and urbanisation in recent decades has led to an increase in the amount of pollution in our water supply. Heavy metals are elements with high density and atomic weight. Iron, lead, mercury, cadmium, zinc, arsenic, copper, and chromium are all examples of heavy metals. Several of them, like iron, cobalt, and zinc, are nourishing in small amounts but poisonous in big ones or in particular forms. Effluents containing heavy metals come from a variety of sources, including the combustion of fossil fuels, the smelting of various metals, municipal trash, fertilisers, pesticides, and sewage [13]. These heavy metals are capable of persisting in the environment and have a tendency of bioaccumulation [14,15, 16]. When these heavy metals enter in aquatic system they not only pollute them but cause serious health effects. This paper will focus on copper, lead and cadmium toxicity, source of these particular heavy metals and their effect on health are mentioned in Table 1.

Banana plant as adsorbent

A banana is an elongated, edible fruit, botanically a berry. The scientific name for banana is *musa sapientum* (Table 2). Huge herbaceous plants, bananas are a popular food and a source of fibre. You won't find any woody stems among these plants. Their big, elongated, bright green leaves are held aloft by fleshy, erect stalks. The lignin and cellulose found in the banana plant's stem, stalk, and leaves boost its efficiency in absorbing metal ions [17]. Because of its takes two steps to make activated carbon: carbonization and activation [19]. The precursor to activated carbon decomposes during carbonization, resulting in a drop in density and an increase in porosity. Biochar is a form of charcoal produced by pyrolyzing (heating to very high temperatures in the absence of oxygen) biomass [20]. Because of its high porosity, biochar has been successfully used in a variety of contexts, including soil enhancement, water treatment, wastewater treatment,

renewable energy, and as a catalyst [21]. Activated carbon and biochar extracted from banana leaves are

effective adsorbents for removing metal ions from water.

Table 1: Heavy metal source and their effect on health

Heavy metal	Permissible limit (WHO) mg/L	Source	Effect	Reference
Cu (II)	1.5	Industrial pollution, domestic wastewater, mining wastewater, and weathering of copper-bearing rocks	Diarrhea, headaches, and in severe cases, kidney failure.	[39]
Pb (II)	0.05	Industries such as mining, steel, automobile, batteries and paints, pesticides, leaded gasoline, and mobile batteries.	Industries such as mining, steel, automobile, batteries and paints, pesticides, leaded gasoline, and mobile batteries	[38]
Cd(II)	0.003	Smelting, metal plating, cadmium-nickel batteries, phosphate fertilizers, pigments, alloy industries and copper refineries , petroleum products refineries, pesticides, plastics, polyvinyl and galvanized pipes production.	Hypertension, dulled sense of smell, anaemia, joint soreness, dry scaly skin, loss of hair and appetite, low production of Tcells and, weak immune system, damage of kidney and liver, emphysema, and cancer	[40]

Table 2: Botanical description of banana plant

Common name	Banana tree
Botanical name	<i>Musa spp.</i>
Family	<i>Musa spp.</i>
Plant type	Herbaceous, perennial
Types	<i>Musa acuminata, Musa ornate, Musa basjoo</i>

Factors affecting adsorption process

Effect of pH

Banana leave powder (BL) and banana leaves activated carbon (BLAC) were utilised as adsorbents by [22] Darweesh to remove copper (II) from aqueous solutions. The pH range of 2--6 was investigated for its effects on the copper adsorption procedure. When the pH was raised from 2 to 6, copper removal efficiency rose from 27% to 46% with BL adsorbent and from 30% to 66% with BLAC. At a pH of 5, BL adsorbent achieved a 52% copper removal efficiency, while BLAC surface removal reached 83%. This could be because a greater quantity of negatively charged adsorbent surface becomes available at higher pH levels, allowing for increased copper adsorption [21].

Banana Stalk Activated Carbon (BSAC) was able to remove Pb (II) at a maximum of 97.9 percent at a pH value of 8. The percentage of Pb (II) removal was 34.97 percent at a pH value of 2, 40.58 percent at a pH value of 5, and 40.979 percent at a pH value of 8. Lead absorption increased as the pH was raised because the electrostatic repulsion between Pb(II) and the BSAC surface site diminished and the BSAC surface became negatively charged, allowing for binding of the Pb(II) cation via electrostatic attraction [23].

Pb (II) and Cd (II) were removed from water using biochar made from banana stems and leaves (BSL-BC) by [24] Liu et al., 2022. Mixtures of 50 mg BSL-BC and 50 mL solutions containing 200 mg/L Pb²⁺ at initial pH (2.0-6.0) in 100 mL were used to examine the effect of pH on Pb²⁺ adsorption, while mixtures of 50 mg BSL-BC and 50 mL solutions containing 50 mg/L Cd²⁺ at initial pH (2.0-6.0) were used to examine the effect of pH on adsorption of Cd²⁺ (2.0–8.0). In their research, they discovered that lead removal was optimal at pH 5 and cadmium removal was best at pH 8.

Effect of adsorbent dose

Process of adsorption depends on adsorbent/solution ratio, which is an indicator for adsorption capacity of adsorbent [25] Copper removal was found to increase from 22% to 59% when the amount of BL was raised from 0.05 to 0.25 gm, and from 26% to 97% when the dose of BLAC was raised from 0.05 to 0.25 gm [22]. Because adsorbents have a greater surface area at higher doses, more active sites are made available in relation to the initial concentration of copper [26]

With an increase in adsorbent dose from 0.05 to 0.2g, the percentage of Pb (II) removed rose from 57 to 98.52%, but the adsorption capacity fell from 114 to 49.26mg/g. It was demonstrated conclusively that, for a given starting solute concentration, an increase in the adsorbent dosage results in an increase in the amount of Pb (II) adsorbed due to an increase in surface area or accessible adsorption sites. The decrease in adsorption capacity with increasing adsorption site concentration throughout the adsorption process is likely due to a lack of metal ions in solution relative to the number of binding sites provided by the adsorbent [23]

Effect of initial concentration

Banana leaves (BL) and banana leave activated charcoal (BLAC) were employed by [22] to remove Copper (II) from water. The results showed that when the Cu (II) concentration was raised from 50 mg/l to 250 mg/l, the adsorption capacity of BL rose from 15 to 39 mg/g and that of BLAC rose from 22.5 to 62.5 mg/g.

Pb (II) concentration doubled from 50 to 250 mg/l, while activated carbon loading capacity tripled from 23.5 to 106 mg/g. As the starting concentration was increased, the adsorption capacity also increased. Pb(II) adsorption rates were high initially because of an abundance of binding sites, but they levelled off after some time [23].

Effect of contact time

It was found that at 100 mg/g of Cu (II) with banana leaves (BL), 30% Cu (II) was adsorbed with 20 min of stirring, and that extending the contact duration increased the Cu (II) removal efficiency. Within 40

minutes, however, 42% of the Cu (II) in the solution had been adsorbed. The sorption effectiveness is nearly same for contact times ranging from 40 to 120 minutes. The results showed that after 20 minutes of stirring, 55% of the Cu (II) ions were removed from a solution with the same concentration of Cu (II) (100 mg/g) as in the control. The percentage of Cu (II) ions removed from the solution increases as contact duration increases, reaching 77% after 60 minutes. Contact times of up to 120 minutes produced results that were nearly as good as those achieved with a shorter contact period of 60 minutes. Because of this, the time required for Cu (II) to be completely removed from the contact was calculated to be 40 minutes for BL and 60 minutes for BLAC [22]

Adsorption of Pb(II) on BSAC was studied by varying the contact time between 50 and 250 minutes. Pb(II) removal increased throughout time and stabilised at a constant value after 120 minutes [23].

Effect of Temperature

Whether or not bioadsorbents are successful in removing metals depends heavily on temperature. In a study conducted by [22], the percentage of copper removed increased from 43% to 65% with BL, and from 72% to 94% with BLAC, as the temperature was raised from 25°C to 40°C. One possible explanation for this result is that copper (II) diffuses more quickly from the solution to the adsorbent surface at higher temperatures [27]. Positive values of H (766.30 J/mol for BL and 1293.9 J/mol for BLAC) and S (2.44 and 4.38 J/mol K for BL and BLAC, respectively) are indicative of the endothermic adsorption of copper onto BL and BLAC, where the copper is being deposited in a random manner. As negative values of G indicate that copper adsorption can occur naturally and is technically feasible [28] Indicating stronger adsorption at higher temperatures, the maximum absorption capacity of lead rose when the temperature was raised. Increased surface activity is to blame for this, as it indicates that Pb(II) adsorption onto BSAC was an exothermic process [23]. Factors affecting metal ion adsorption on adsorbent is shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Comparative study of metal ion adsorption on Banana plant

Pollutant	Plant part used as adsorbent	pH	Adsorbent dose	Initial concentration	Contact time	Temp	Adsorption capacity	Adsorption model used	Kinetic model used	Reference
Cu (II)	Banana leave powder	5	0,25g	50, 100, 150, 200, and 250 mg/L	40 min	40 ⁰ C	48.7 mg/g	Langmuir model	Pseudo-second-order kinetics and Elovich model together with the intraparticle diffusion phenomenon	[22]
	Banana leaves activated carbon	5	0,25g	50, 100, 150, 200, and 250 mg/L	60 min	40 ⁰ C	66.2 mg/g	Langmuir model		
Pb (II)	Banana Stalk Activated Carbon (BSAC)	8	0.05 to 0.2g	250 mg/l	120 min	50 ⁰ C	200 mg/g	Langmuir model	Pseudo-second-order	[23]
Pb (II)	Biochar prepared from	5	50 mg	200 mg/L	8 hrs	-	302.2 mg/g	Langmuir model	Pseudo-second-order	[24]
Cd (II)	Banana stem & leaves	8	50 mg	50 mg/L	200 min		32.03 mg/g	Langmuir model	Pseudo-second-order	

Isothermal and kinetic study of metal adsorption on biomass

Isothermal study of metal adsorption

The adsorption isotherm is a function obtained by measuring the amount of material adsorbed as a function of concentration at a constant temperature. Several different adsorption isotherms exist, each describing a unique aspect of the process. Several functional groups on the adsorbent's surface, as well as the presence of adsorbent-adsorbate interaction, are reflected in the Freundlich model as sources of surface heterogeneity [29]. The creation of a monolayer of adsorbate on an adsorbent surface is described quantitatively by the Langmuir adsorption isotherm [30,31,32]. The Temkin isotherm model predicts that, due to the interaction between the adsorbent and the adsorbate, the heat of adsorption decreases linearly rather than logarithmically when the concentration gradient across the layer is covered [33] [34]. Low-coverage energetic heterogeneity, such as monolayer areas in micropores, has been widely explained using the [35,36] Dubinin-Radushkevich equation. The production of an adsorbate monolayer on the surface of activated carbon and biochar generated from banana leaves, stems, and stalks was demonstrated by the Langmuir adsorption isotherm (Table 3).

Kinetic models for batch adsorption

Adsorption kinetics explains the solute intake rate, which regulates the residence duration of the adsorbate uptake at the solid-solution interface, which includes the diffusion process. There is a correlation between the mass transfer process and the physical and chemical properties of the adsorbents, both of which influence the adsorption mechanism. Reaction-based models can be presented as pseudo first-order and pseudo second-order models for metal ion removal from aqueous solution by adsorbent, while diffusion-based models can be presented as particle diffusion and intraparticle diffusion models. Table 4 provides the mathematical formulae for these models, which include factors like the adsorption capacity q_e , particle diffusion constant k_p , intraparticle diffusion constant k_{diff} , and intercept C . (Table 4) displays the results of an application of the Elovich model to the adsorption process; a gives the initial adsorption rate ($\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) and b gives the activation energy and surface coverage (mg/g).

Pseudo-second-order kinetics, the Elovich model, and the intraparticle diffusion phenomenon all applied to the adsorption of Cu (II) on banana leaf powder and banana leaf activated carbon, but only pseudo-second-order kinetics applied to the adsorption of Pb (II) and Cd (II) on Biochar prepared from Banana stem & leaves (Table 3).

Table 4: Isothermal and kinetic models for adsorption

Type of Model	Model	Mathematical Equation	Linearized form	Reference
Isothermal	Langmuir	$q_s = K_F C_s^{1/n}$	$\log q_s = \log K_F + \frac{1}{n} \log C_s$	[30], [31]
	Freundlich	$q_s = \frac{Q_0 K_L C_s}{1 + K_L C_s}$	$\frac{C_s}{q_s} = \frac{1}{Q_0 K_L} + \frac{C_s}{Q_0}$	[30] [29]
	Temkin	$q_s = \frac{RT}{b_T \ln(A_T C_s)}$	$q_s = B_T \ln A_T + B_T \ln C_s$ ($B_T = RT/b_T$)	[30] [33] [34]
	Dubinin-Radushkevich	$q_e = q_s e^{-\beta \varepsilon^2}$	$\ln q_e = \ln q_s - \beta \varepsilon^2$ $\varepsilon = RT \ln(1/C_e)$	[30] [35] [36]
Kinetic (Reaction based)	Pseudo-first order	$\frac{dq_t}{dt} = k_1 (q_s - q_t)$	$\log(q_s - q_t) = \log(q_s) - \frac{k_1}{2.303} t$	[37] [22]
	Pseudo second order	$\frac{dq_t}{dt} = k_2 (q_s - q_t)^2$	$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_s^2} + \frac{t}{q_s}$	[37] [22]
Kinetic (Diffusion based)	Particle diffusion	$\frac{C_t}{C_s} = 1 - e^{-k_p t}$	$\ln\left(1 - \frac{C_t}{C_s}\right) = -k_p t$	[37] [22]
	Intra particle diffusion	$\frac{dq_t}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} k_{diff} q_t^{-1/2}$	$q_t = k_{diff} t^{1/2} + C$	[37] [22]
	Elovich model	$q_t = 1/b \{ \ln(abt) + 1 \}$	$q_t = 1/b \ln(ab) + 1/b \ln t$	[22]

Mechanism of adsorption on parts of Banana plant

X-ray diffraction (XRD) is a characterisation technique used in the analysis of phase and crystal structure that has the benefit of being fingerprint-suitable. Banana leaves' X-ray diffraction patterns exhibited two prominent peaks at 16.55 and 22.55, indicating the existence of native cellulose as the primary component. Cellulose can exist either in crystalline or amorphous form. Two broad diffraction peaks at 26 and 44 degrees, corresponding to (0 0 2) and (1 01) planes, respectively, describe the amorphous nature of the activated carbons made from banana leaves. The amorphous nature of the adsorbent made it easier for the metal ion to diffuse through the material [22].

X-ray diffraction examination revealed that BSL-BC had crystals of CaCO₃ and CaC₂O₄ (H₂O) on its surface prior to adsorption. CdCO₃ and CdC₂O₄ crystals were found on the Cd-loaded BSL-BC, while PbC₂O₄ crystals formed on the Pb-loaded BSL-BC after adsorption [24].

The functional groups of adsorbents can be determined by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and this information can then be used to predict the nature of the adsorbent's interactions with the heavy metal ions that it will be used to remove.

The IR spectra pattern of the BL showed unique and abrupt absorptions due to the existence of the -OH, -CH, -C-O- and -C- -O groups, while the adsorption peaks

displayed for BL and BLAC before and after adsorption of copper ions were different. The BL functional groups responsible for Cu (II) adsorption are to blame for these bands [22].

The O-H group of carboxylic acid in raw banana stalk (RBS) produces a band at 3302.82 cm⁻¹ in FTIR analysis, but in banana stalk activated carbon, this same group produces a band at 3390.74 cm⁻¹ (BSAC). The aliphatic C-H group contributes a band at 2918–2323.47 cm⁻¹ for RBS and a band at 2822–2383.53 cm⁻¹ for BSAC. FTIR examination of Raw Banana Stalk (RBS) and BSAC shows that there is a variation in bands, wave numbers, and absorbance between the RBS and BSAC samples, showing that a chemical transformation occurred during chemical treatment and carbonization. Throughout the process of transforming RBS into BSAC, a variety of changes occurred, including the strengthening and weakening of functional groups, the shifting and weakening of wavelength numbers, and so on [23]

After coming into contact with Pb²⁺ or Cd²⁺, the FTIR spectra of BSL-BC demonstrate that the C-O absorption peak (1318 cm⁻¹) is shifted to the right, and the -OH peak (3430 cm⁻¹) is significantly diminished. There was a noticeable attenuation of these two peaks on Cd²⁺-loaded BSL-BC, as well. Because of their consumption

Conflict of Interest

Author(s) declared no conflict of interest.

Ethical Compliance Standard

NA.

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during Pb²⁺ and Cd²⁺ adsorption, oxygen-containing functional groups are likely involved in complexation with the metal ions [24]

Conclusion

Activated carbon made from banana leaves, BSAC made from banana stalks, and biochar made from banana leaves and stems all have sufficient adsorptive characteristics for the removal of Cu (II), Pb (II), and Cd (II) from aqueous environments. The initial metal ion concentration, temperature, contact time, pH, and adsorbent dosage all play roles in the adsorption of various heavy metals on banana based adsorbent. Researchers analysed equilibrium adsorption data using the Langmuir, Freundlich, Temkin, and Dubinin-Radushkevich (D-R) isotherm models, but only the Langmuir isotherm model showed a strong correlation with the data, suggesting that metal ions are adsorbed in monolayers on homogeneous adsorbent surfaces. In conjunction with the intraparticle diffusion phenomena, the adsorption process was endothermic and spontaneous. According to Fourier-infrared spectroscopy, the adsorbents made from banana leaves, stalks, and stems feature abundant functional groups on surfaces, which may account for the adsorption of metal ions via metal-H ion exchange or metal ion surface complexation adsorption, or even both.

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